

Christianity in Nigeria and Political Challenges 1960–2020

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Abstract

The Study examines Christianity in Nigeria and political challenges 1960 – 2020. It is certain that Christianity in Nigeria has achieved a number of developments since its inception up to date and with these attributes, the religion has played some vital roles in the development and integration of Nigeria. While the faith has enormously touched the social life of the people, it seems not to have much effect on the political life of Nigerians. Much expectation of Nigerians is on Christian faith and its leadership to help in molding the society in a way to achieve success in appointment and election of good leaders. However, the opposite has remained the case. So worrisome is that many Christian politicians are into some defiant acts such as thuggery, electoral rigging, fetishes and syncretic activities, murder and gross thirst for materialism. In this way several Christian values which had helped in the integration of the nation are now being commonised and politicalised to the detriment of both Christianity as a religion and the political state of Nigeria. The thrust of this paper is to take a look into the interaction of Christianity and Nigeria politics, with the aim of bringing to light some salient ways the faith has impeded the political success of Nigeria. The study finds out that there is every hope that if the Christian values like godliness, purity, unity, love etc. are practiced as well preached by Christian leaders, this will go a long way to breed a better political generations. This paper utilized qualitative methodology and therefore involved sociological and historical approaches and as such, has solely depended on secondary source for gathering of data such as books, journals article and internet materials.

Introduction

Nigeria currently, is in dire need of viable, credible leadership and it is common knowledge among Nigerians that the main challenge to the growth and development of the nation is how to raise such leadership through the necessary political process of election. In the past, Christianity has been known to have some fundamental doctrines and laudable values like godliness, honesty, unity and a high level of morality which were highly and jealously appreciated among the Nigerian people. With these attributes, Christianity has played some vital and integral roles in the development of the Nation Nigeria with several worthwhile innovations orchestrated. Thus, impacts of Christianity in almost all spheres of human life and endeavours in Africa have formed the heading of several academic works in Nigerian tertiary institutions, making the history of Nigeria replete with the account of the impact of Christianity on its development. It is glaring to recognize that the African's early elites in all spheres of life have testimonies and experiences gained from interactions with the early Christian missionaries or the early Christian established social institutions such as schools.

It is indeed very true that there is no part of the African life, be it social, economic, religious and cultural aspects that Christian values have not impacted. It is to the extent that the percolation and animation of all aspects of African life by Christian values reached an enviable state which made African scholars begin to call for de-

Christianisation of African values, which they claimed to have been dragged to near extinction on the account of Christian influence on it. Christianity, in all its forms and versions, has actually impacted African people, especially Nigerians. Christianity has continued to be praised for several positive impacts it had brought on the African people until recently that some areas of their impacts are beginning to be discovered with some ills. One of these areas that Christianity seemed to have a less or adverse impact is the political life of the nation Nigeria. It is expected by the Nigerian populace in recent times that given the unabated proliferation of churches, denominations and wide range of Christian activities and values in Nigeria, the nation should have been better politically. This idea has been stressed in many African write-ups in recent times. This is because the Nigerian political leaders over the years have failed to bring the dividends of responsible leadership to the populace. The Nigerian road networks are bad just as electricity is almost non-existent.¹ The educational system is in shamble. So, also is the health system. The youth remain hopeless while the aged are miserable. The people live in abject poverty amid plenty as the Nigerian successive governments have continued to deceive the whole world that things have been so good for the people.²

While much expectation of Nigerians is on the Christian faith and its leadership to help in moulding the society in a way to achieve success in the appointment and election of good leaders, the opposite has remained the case. So worrisome is the involvement of Christian politicians in some defiant acts such as thuggery, electoral rigging, fetishes and syncretic activities, murder and gross thirst for materialism. More worrisome is the attitude of church leaders in Nigeria. Their attitude towards political gladiators of the Nigerian state, however, leaves much to be desired, in the writer's judgments. The Christian leaders in Nigeria seem to have resolved to be on the side of the political elite. Except for very few in recent times, many Christian leaders are hardly critical of bad government policies. Due to the unchristian attitude of Christians towards politics in Nigeria, several traditional Christian values were shaken to the foundation, jettisoned, and corrupted. These Christian values which have helped in the integration of the nation are now being politicalised to the detriment of both Christianity as a religion and the political state of the nation.³

This paper is aimed at examining Christianity in Nigeria and political challenges since 1960 to 2020. 1960 is the beginning of the consideration of the sixty years analysis of this topic. It will also take a look at the political state of Nigeria to bring to light some of the salient activities of Christians, especially the Christian leaders that impede the political success of the nation Nigeria. The reason for the time frame of 1960 – 2020 is that the year 1960 was when Nigeria got its independence and the nation became a republic in 1963. Sixty years consideration of this topic ends in 2020. The time frame suits well for this research because the responsibility of leadership largely depended on the dictates of the British government at this period.⁴ But political processes began when the nation became a republic as stated above. The paper utilized sociological and historical approaches, and as such, has solely depended on secondary source for gathering of data such as books, journal articles, and internet materials.

Christianity in Nigeria

The first attempt at bringing Christianity to the geographical entity now called Nigeria was the initiative of the Portuguese during the period of exploration. The Portuguese King was interested in converting to Christianity the people of West Africa who were assigned to him through the Papal Bull of Demarcation. Though the conversion of this territory to the Catholic faith was not the main aim of the Portuguese expeditions in the fifteenth century, it constituted a very integral mission that became so imperative to the King. The priests who came from Portugal to meet with the traditional rulers in the African Kingdom had with them letters of accreditation. The missionaries never intended to settle and reside among the people, learn their language and customs and then convert them to Christianity. They intended to convert the Kings and make them pass a decree, making the Catholic faith the religion of their kingdoms. The strategy was for the conversion of as many people as possible in Africa, especially the Benin Kingdom. But quite, unfortunately, this strategy could not win many people to Christianity as envisaged. Among other reasons, the missionaries were more representative of the political authority of the King

of Portugal than the Catholic Church. They were so ignorant of the religious customs of Africans, which they tagged as the worship of the devil (diabolism).⁵

The kind of Christianity which the Portuguese sought to spread to West Africa was the Catholic variety, developed in the culture of Western Europe and which particularly embodied the cultural values of the Iberian Peninsula. Conversion, according to the Portuguese, was by implication the adoption of a particular pattern of daily life. Their focus was the transformation of great areas of Africa into faithful but carbon copies of Portugal.⁶ Apart from this dubious strategy, as other factor responsible for this initial failure was the difficulties in understanding the language of the natives by the European missionaries and the use of interpreters to evangelize the natives. This, in most cases, created barriers in transmitting the gospel message to the natives, as interpreters were likely not to comprehend the true meaning of the message. The poor transportation system in the hinterlands was also an impediment to the planting of Christianity at that earlier period. They trekked on foot or rode on horses through the bushes. This was tiring and energy-consuming, and as a result, they did very little.⁷

The period was marked by the general concept that Africa was the “white man’s grave” as a result of several tropical diseases particularly malaria. This disease resulted in the death of many missionaries but was eased out when quinine was discovered in 1854. There was a funding problem: the missionaries experienced this because most of them were on their own. There was no support for those sent to Africa from their country home. The main problem was also that the missionaries did not understand the culture of the natives, and, therefore, assumed that Africans were without culture and traditional practices and so sought to transform the natives into a carbon copy of the white people. Africans, with all vehemence resisted this. Their resistance impeded the missionary work. Thus, Ryder states, “Not one of the Christian missionaries, for all their devotion, came near an adequate understanding of the complex religious system they were trying to displace”⁸

Despite this failure, it is on record that from the 19th century there were traces of Christian influence in West Africa. For example, a few relics like the hung cross and decoration materials surviving around the traditional shrines in Benin, Warri and Owerri, were found to be evidence of Christian influence in the nineteenth century. It was the nineteenth-century missionary efforts that sustained the growth of Christianity in West Africa. Lere comments further, on this note, that the early Christian Missionary endeavour in 1841 – 1842 marked the beginning of the movement to re-establish Christianity in West Africa, after the failure of the earlier attempts in 1482. The impetus behind the success story of the later missionary movements was the evangelical revival of the eighteenth century.⁹

In November 1837, about twenty-three leading Yoruba merchants led by Thomas Will presented to Governor Darchor ideas similar to that of Buxton:

The humble petitions feel very thankful to almighty God and the Queen of England, who had rescued us from being in a state of Slavery and has brought us to this colony and set us at liberty and thanks to the God of all mercy... that the queen will graciously sympathize with her humble petitioners and beg her royal majesty to send missionaries with us and by so doing the slave trade can be abolished... so that the gospel of Christ be preached throughout the land....¹⁰

One of such letters of plea is said to have been written by James Ferguson inviting the missionaries to visit urgently and desiring that the gospel of Christ the saviour may be preached unto her: that schools be built, that Bible be sent, that the British flag is hoisted and that she ranks among the civilized nations of the world. The Methodist mission responded to this request first. They sent Thomas Berch Freeman, an energetic superintendent of the Methodist mission of Ghana, to occupy Badagry as an outstation. His arrival on 24th September 1842 marked the beginning of activities of Christianity in Nigeria. William De Graft accompanied him. He bought a piece of land and at once built a temporary Bamboo chapel which cost \$3000 pounds. Freeman later visited Abeokuta and was received by Chief Sodeke.¹¹

The action of the Methodist mission led other missionary bodies to send their members particularly to where the recaptives continued to settle at their original home place. The Church Missionary Society sent their missionaries to take care of their members among the immigrants. They sent Henry Townsend who had earlier

wished to undertake the 1841 Niger mission but turned it down in favour of Crowder. He came in with “Willberforce” with fifty-nine emigrants on 4th January 1843, at Abeokuta. He was impressed with Sodoke’s reception of the liberated slaves as members of the society of Abeokuta. In 1848 the main CMS mission team arrived at Badagary consisting of Samuel Ajayi Crowther, Gouma, with Marsch, Philips and many others. Other missionary bodies like the Baptist, Presbyterians and the Roman Catholic Mission also responded. Thus, Badagry became the first Missionary base in Nigeria in the nineteenth century. From there the missionaries penetrated the interior parts of Nigeria.¹²

Apart from the efforts of the Methodists, Baptists, CMS, and the Roman Catholics, other missionary bodies came into interior parts of Nigeria such as the Qua’Ibo Mission with their activities in Calabar, and Akwa Ibom areas. This same mission extended its tentacles to Igala and Igbolands in the later years. The Christian Mission in Many Lands (CMML) is another missionary body that arrived in Igala, Idoma, and Egede lands. This same mission extended their activities to complement the efforts of the CMS, RCM, Methodists, and Baptists in northern Nigeria.¹³

The main activities of these missionaries were planting churches and raising indigenous church leaders. Consequently, a good number of churches were planted everywhere the missionaries went. Another thing the missionaries did was focus on the development of the Nigerian society: they helped in establishing western education which is up till today their greatest impact apart from the establishment of churches to cater for the people’s spiritual problems. The church in hand with the early missionaries helped to develop our Health delivery system by bringing in the modern health delivery system. In no time, western education has brought many social infrastructural developments to Nigeria. The legal system and modern security system were developed as well. The local languages of the people were developed with many translation works carried out by these missionaries. It is also interesting to know that several developments in technology in Nigeria were initiatives of these missionaries. The need for brief assessment of the history of how Christianity came to Nigeria here is to show the integral efforts of Christianity in the formation of the nation Nigeria-as well as put to light that Christianity has been a strong force behind the political evolution of the nation Nigeria from the onset.¹⁴

These and many more were the basic features of the activities of the early missionaries in Nigeria. In the following passage, the study will consider the state of the Nigerian nation before the advent of these missionaries as this will make us to appreciate the early contributions of the missionaries to the political formation of the African states including Nigeria.¹⁵

Political Challenges in Nigeria

Nigeria is a country that has everything it needs to stand tall and lead from the front. Yet it ranks among the poorest countries of the world. The unfortunate case is that Nigeria is one of the most religious countries of the world, yet she is one of the most corrupt nations of the world. Nigeria’s socio-economic conditions, therefore, present a startling paradox: despite a rich endowment of natural and human resources, most parts of the country are poor. For decades the country has struggled to improve socio- economic conditions, which have declined despite increasing revenue from crude oil. The growing incidence and the dynamics of poverty in Nigeria have stratified and polarised Nigerian society between the haves and the have-nots, between the South and North, between educated and the uneducated. Poor parents beget children, creating a kind of dynasty of the poor. The resulting tensions, class struggle and social conflicts have eroded the fabric that held the Nigerian society together.¹⁶ Nigeria is said to be a country that many others would wish they were as blessed with natural and human resources as presently obtained in Nigeria. The question now is, how has Nigeria gotten into its present predicament? Why is Nigeria with all these enviable natural and human resources still among the developing (third world) countries?¹⁷

Achebe stated that the trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a problem of leadership. According to him, the Nigerian problem is the unwillingness or inability of its leaders to rise to the responsibility of the challenge of personal example, which are the hallmarks of true leadership.¹⁸ Usman agrees with Achebe that bad

leadership is the bane to the growth of the nation. He further opines that “the main problems hindering our progress in almost all areas of endeavour are the leadership and the bad system of governance”. Usman believes we have had a succession of evil leadership, which has continued to unleash tyranny and deprivation on the masses. He expresses the grief and plight of the people, and paints a gory picture of a country perching precariously on the brink of disaster because the leaders have turned leadership into a curse.¹⁹ This is perhaps what Ehusani had in mind when he wrote his heart-rending piece, “Nigeria: years Eaten by Locust”. He notes how the inept and corrupt leadership is running Nigeria aground. Yet he is optimistic that God can still rescue the country from the locusts and madmen in high places.²⁰

It has also been investigated that bad leadership does not just emerge in a society, but it is the by-product and a reflection of what the society has turned to. The way bad leaders emerge in Nigeria should be another concern to us. Our political process from which leaders emerge in Nigeria is porous, sick and an aberration of what political process should be. In all of the regimes from the 1st October 1960 that Nigeria got her independence, till date, the cry of every incoming regime is that they have come to eradicate corruption found with the former regime. Ige gave a clear analysis of each of the regimes’ promises at their takeover of government and how each of them failed abysmally on the account of being swallowed by the public corruption they try to eradicate. It is lamentable and an obvious indication that Nigeria’s political process is so corrupt to the extent that it cannot produce viable, corrupt free and patriotic leadership.²¹

This is because the electorates have been weakened by intimidation through political killing (Assassination), thuggery, kidnapping and other societal ills that characterized the electoral processes in the nation. There is also vote buying, rigging of elections and all sort of electoral manipulations in the Nigerian elections. Hence, there is a need to begin to sanitize the Nigerian populace to awaken them into the consciousness of these ills. This is the task the Christian Church must be into. The church has to intensify its effort towards restoring sanity first to the populace and then to Nigerian leadership at large.²²

The Christian involvement in Nigerian Contemporary Politics

Religion has always played a significant role in influencing political participation in Nigeria. In fact, "Religion has long served as a political resource in Nigeria, with Muslims and Christians alike appealing to the faithful, and decrying each other, to win elections."²³ Christianity's incursion into politics started in 1949 when “Christians of the Middle-Belt in the North, upon their increased perception of discrimination and gross dissatisfaction with the ‘Islamic reign’ of the NPC-led government under the leadership of Ahmadu Bello (an ardent of the ‘One North, One People’ agenda) mobilized themselves to challenge the rule”²⁴ The first attempt by the Christians in this direction was the establishment of the Northern Nigerian Non-Muslim League following a motion raised in 1949 on the floor of the Northern House of Assembly for the restriction of the activities of the Christian missionaries. Dudley posits that this league while relying on the unflinching support of the Christian missions in the country provided the template for the formation of the Middle Zone League (MZL) as a political party with its primary motive of resisting any northern Islamization agenda.²⁵

Within this context, it became increasingly clear to Christians that Northern elites had no plans of insulating Islam from politics. Thus, within the Christian community, this struggle for freedom found expression in the setting up of the Northern Christian Association. Its objectives were the protection and preservation of the rights of Christians in the North. It is important to note of course that this was in keeping with the regional nature of the politics of the time²⁶. The earliest and full appearance of Christianity on political front is shown in accusation of some scholars that the 1966 Coup d'états was motivated by Christian interest in politics in Nigeria.

Some scholars like Gumi & Tsiga, Onabanjo have argued that Christianity further instigated political participation and reshaped the political landscape of Nigeria through military coups. While Gumi and Tsiga alluded to the 1966 *coup d'etas* to be religiously motivated, Onabanjo suggested that the 1990 coup equally had religion as its underpinnings. This position sounds convincing when we consider Falola's arguments that Muslims from the North accused the Christian Association of Nigeria to be the architects of the 1990 abortive *coup d'etas*

and the then military president Ibrahim Babangida unofficially indicted the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and detained 59 of its members for two months on account of the abortive coup. The above shows the earlier interest of Christianity in politics and leadership in Nigeria. It is then obvious that Christianity had not been fully committed to politics and leadership of the Nation as early as expected. Rather than being intentionally committed to politics, and have much impact on the electoral processes, Christianity's involvement was circumstantial in most cases.²⁸

It is noticeable that full commitment and participation of Christians in politics in Nigeria is very recent. This is not to say that Christians have not been contesting for political post, neither were Christians not being involved in voting for candidates of their choice. But it is certain that Christianity in its early days in Nigeria was not in full consciousness that it retains some ethical values that can contribute to political development of Nigeria. It is only in recent time that Christianity has begun to actively participate in politics. Its circumstantial involvement in politics in the past made the Muslim clerics and some intellectual minds sees the recent Christian active involvement in politics as suspicious. Rather than objective motives, Christian's involvement in politics is seen with subjective motivation to singularly counter their perceived intention that the Muslim leaders want to Islamize Nigeria.²⁹

In terms of registering for elections, religious leaders play significant roles in sensitizing, educating and encouraging their followers to register and vote. In Nigeria, election years in recent times are usually preceded by months of civic theologies by both Christian Clergies and Muslim Imams, admonishing their followers on the need for them to exercise their civic responsibilities. Depending on the person preaching (whether he is a Muslim or a Christian), such theologies of civic responsibilities are usually interlaced with an emphasis by the preacher on who they perceive to constitute a better candidate in the election. This is especially the case with the Nigeria presidential elections where the major contestants are usually Muslim and Christian. The trajectory has always been that Christian clergies will admonish their followers to vote for a Christian. Conversely, an Imam will recommend the Muslim candidate for the Muslims.

One example will suffice. In the heat of the campaigns for the 2019 Presidential elections, David Abioye, a Senior Pastor of Winner's Chapel in one of his sermons is quoted to have said "we must wake up. We must wake up. 2019 must be deciding year for the church. We must wake up. We'll not use our hands to vote for people who'll kill us. We'll not vote for people who have value for cows more than value for human lives. Wake up. A word is enough for the wise". Many of these calls were all over the church denominations. And on the other hand, the Muslim clerics were also canvassing for their followers to vote for Muslim candidates.³⁰

Another way Christianity has been used as a tool of political mobilization is by having religious figures participate in elections as candidates. This equally plays out in the Nigerian setting. Religion makes incursions into politics when religious leaders contest for electoral positions or pair themselves as running mates of some other politicians. Under such circumstances, these religious leaders galvanise support from their congregation to vote for the party under whose platform they are running. In the 2011 and 2015 presidential elections in Nigeria, the current president of Nigeria ran for the presidential race with two different Senior Pastors of leading Pentecostal churches: Tunde Bakare and Yemi Osinbajo respectively. While he lost the race with Tunde Bakare in 2011, he won the 2015 elections with Yemi Osinbajo. Similarly, Christ Okotie, the senior pastor of Household of God church has been running as a presidential candidate since 2003. These pastors used their leadership position in the church to prevail on their members to vote for them and their political parties.³¹

From the foregoing, it is clear that Christianity was insulated from politics and therefore was not actively involved in partisan politics from the early days of its inception in Nigeria. But it began full participation in 1949 with protest against the ruling party's seeming intention to Islamize the Nation. Christian leaders since then have continued to mobilize Christians to participate in politics both as voters and electoral candidates at all levels possible. With this development, it looks like Christian consciousness had been awakened towards politics. However, this seems not to be enough as the electoral processes in Nigeria have been corrupted to the extent that

it will be difficult if not impossible for a good Christian to emerge in any position of leadership while still maintaining his conviction as a Christian without corruption and compromise.

The submission of this paper is that in addition to the discussed roles played by Christians in Nigerian politics, there is a need to infiltrate the political spaces with Christian values that have helped in integration of the nation in the past. While the Christians call for their full participation in politics, Christians notable values such as honesty, truthfulness, patriotism, love, humility, selflessness and many others should be emphasized as their watch-words in politics. In doing this, the following problems identified with Christianity in relation to political challenges in Nigeria should be addressed:

i. Failure to correct the mistakes of the early days of Ignorance among Christians

The first and earliest way Christianity has contributed to the political dilemma of the nation Nigeria is the discouragement of the earliest converts of the faith from active partisan politics. It was a display of ignorance on the side of the early Christian missionaries in Nigeria to take politics as a dirty game. According to Boer, 'at the world missionary conference of 1910, it was agreed that missionaries should abstain from politics in dealing with the colonial government and the local people. The missionaries were taught and commanded to preach the gospel and also be involved in the provision of social services in education and health care delivery, but should not encourage Christians (their converts) to go into politics and business.'³²

In obedience in this injunction, in spite of the significance of politics and political leadership in the life of the people, right from the time of the colonialists until the seventies, politics was not thought to be for Christians but for non-Christians only. Very few Christians ventured to go into politics and those who did were not thought to be good Christians. The few therefore who joined politics then, learned to do it the world's way or the unchristian way. For this reason, politics and governance in Nigeria is virtually seen from a secular or non-Christian perspective and anyone who dares to practice it the Christian way is ridiculed, ignored and called names or thought not to be a good Christian or a good politician. According to Musa, many good and faithful Nigerian Christians who God would have used or wished to be in politics and political leadership shy away from it because of the dirty trend of politics in Nigeria. The adverse effect of this early stand of Christians is so severe that even though the Christian faith has helped in moulding the nation in several respects as seen above, the religion itself became a late corner in active politics in Nigeria.³³

In the consequence, the Christian values that upheld the integration and grass root formation of the nation were not brought to bear in the politics and leadership of the nation. Musa could not hold his grief on this issue when he lamented that Christianity had all it takes to bridge the ever-widening, increasing, elasticizing gaps between the poor and the rich if adequate measures were taken by the early Christian elites of the nation. Adamo added that as Christians, we should expect that ways of getting good, godly and god-fearing leaders lie in our hands more than any religion. On this note, the researcher wishes to submit that, if the early Nigerian Christians have had the freedom to participate actively in the process of choosing their leaders, in the same way Christian values impacted education and health sector, it would have impacted Nigerian politics positively.³⁴

(ii) Corruption and Compromise among Christians and Christian Politicians

It is observable that when Christians had awakened into consciousness on the need to participate fully in politics, the faith encountered the problem of corruption. As earlier mentioned, the greatest problem of Nigeria is bad and inept leadership. However, bad leadership, to a large extent, is a reflection of a bad society. It takes bad politics to breed bad leadership. How corruption got into the Nigerian system is not the focus of this study here but corruption has certainly been in the system of government in Nigeria right from the colonial and through the post-colonial governments. However, it was limited to governance and was very minimal in human society. But currently, it is a much-known fact that corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of Nigerian society. Starting from the colonial era in Nigeria, corruption has made constant seemingly uncontrollable progress up to the present. There is hardly any administration in Nigeria's history that has not been accused of this social incubus. The underprivileged no doubt are the victims of corruption at the earlier state, while the ruling class hypocritically pretend to be involved in the fight against corruption.

But in the recent past, the vast majority of Nigerians have learnt and experimented in bribery and corruption at various levels. Corruption in Nigeria, therefore, seems to have become a way of life in the daily activities of Nigerians. How can Christianity dominate in education and health care delivery and every other social institution and fail in breeding a generation of godly people? Olusegun Obasanjo while wondering on the same line of thought has completely agreed that corruption is like cancer and cankerworm which has eaten deep into the fabric of Nigeria. He identified the church as an important and influential institution in our society that can fight corruption to a reasonable extent, because to him, the main problems are moral, ethical and attitudinal and disorientation. However, he recognized that the failure of Christianity in recent time, to provide and exchange sound moral living and ethical standards for all behaviours makes it difficult for the Christians to influence viable leadership in Nigeria. Today, it has been a great growing and alarming concern particularly in democratic societies of which the Christians cannot be left out. Even the young Christians in the current times are being influenced negatively by some rich Christians. Some of these young persons are being used as thugs to perpetrate and advance selfish ambitions of these politicians. As a result, there is much killing, kidnapping, electoral rigging activities like ballot box snatching, etc., even more perpetrated by Christians.³⁵

Adegbite added a voice when he agreed that the moral standard of an average Nigerian is low. This is to say that our country is corrupt to the core and that stands out as a true image of Nigeria to the outside world. The present state of our public morality shows that even Christianity itself is not freed from corruption. From the look of things in Nigeria, there is every indication that Christianity in recent times has lost its focus on the need to breed good citizens who can be capable of raising good leadership. The need for moral character in the fight against corruption cannot be overemphasized in the personal life of the individual members of the state. This is the foundation that anchors success. This research submits clearly that social growth and development can only be predicted on the solid and sound moral qualities of the citizens³⁶. Therefore, it is a factual statement that no national political disaster or corruption can befall a nation endowed with moral integrity and spirit of self-sacrifice and which respects good behaviour and condemns evil without compromise.³⁷

(iii) Quest for Material Wealth among Christians

Another salient problem that contemporary Christianity has been accused of, is materialism, that is, the uncontrollable quest for material wealth, be it money or properties. It is very glaring that behind any corrupt act in Nigeria is materialism. More than any religion in Nigeria, Christianity has been more indicted for materialism. Materialism tends to undermine hard work, diligence and commitment to business and career which are hallmarks to success in life. Materialism also presupposes that money (wealth) can be made in a shorter time with the aid of political influence than any other means. This explains the greed of the present Nigerians. It is important to state here, that Christianity from the onset in Nigeria was not known to the problem of materialism. It is common knowledge in Nigeria that materialism or its display in much quantum as it is today is very recent. And to be specific, it came with Pentecostalism, even though some scholars have contended that materialism in the Nigerian context was rooted in the excesses of the African Independent Churches.³⁸

Materialism negates what Christianity stood for at the beginning. In the early days of Christianity in Nigeria, it was a religion of the slaves, the outcasts, the poor and the oppressed, as Jesus himself was born in a manger and therefore, was poor. His entire ministry was devoted to fighting the cause of the poor and downtrodden.³⁹ The activities of Christianity in recent time shows its tolerance for material wealth and therefore, exposes the majority of the poor people to exploitative acts, in their search for the elusive breakthrough and miracles, while on the other hand, it emboldens venality and misconduct by public officials who enjoy protection largely because of the easy adaptability of Nigerian patron-client network. It is noticeable and observable that a good number of Christian politicians are guilty of materialism. Materialism has led to the existence of unhealthy competition, not only between Christian politicians but also among clergymen in Nigeria and surprisingly, there is manipulation and exploitation of Christian doctrines going on, especially among the Pentecostals.⁴⁰

Akinola and Obiora have lent their voices as they agreed that the-get-rich-quick syndrome: the desire to get rich quick through any means is widespread among many Nigerians, especially the Christian politicians.

According to Akinola, this attitude is encouraged by how Nigerians tend to glorify the rich no matter how they acquire their wealth. This becomes very obvious and apparent in the way the Christians in most Pentecostal churches honour politicians in giving them seats in high places during worship.⁴¹ Obiora clearly states that the implication of materialism on Christianity has continued to present the religion in a bad light. He added that marketing God is fast becoming a top bracket business...when you go to see a man of God, who develops power, sees past, present and future, you pay the gate fee and also the consultation fee and that is only a preamble. This statement indicates how materialism has come with unhealthy and unscriptural ways of acquiring wealth among Nigerian contemporary ministers. In the same vein, the research submits here that materialism is behind thuggery, political murder and assassination, vote-buying, electoral rigging and many other social ills that pervade the current Nigerian electoral system of which Christian youths and politicians are also guilty. These social ills have continued to fuel disorderliness in our current electoral processes.⁴²

(iv) Denominationalism and disunity among Christians

Arising from the quest for material things among the Nigerian Christian leaders and clergymen is unhealthy competition among them. The competition is much and has led to disunity in the body of Christ. The disunity exists among members as well as among church leaders. According to Odey, our problem as Christians in Nigeria is neither Boko Haram nor the Devil. This author maintained that we can face the devil and shame him. But he sowed the seed of discord and disunity among us.⁴³ Jesutunwase affirmed this assertion that “you will find out that ministers in this country are not united. He added that ministers would rather die than work together for God. Evangelism, which is the heartbeat of God has been misprioritized by church leaders and members in Nigeria, while the priority of the church in this dispensation is on materialism, gifts from both members and non-Christian politicians. In the past, reasons for discord and division were doctrinal controversies, leading to schism and its end product of denominationalism, but in the case of the Nigerian church, it is materialism, pride and human ego. So that even though there is a proliferation of more denominations, there is a loss of power and one voice within the church.⁴⁴ The implication of the discord and disunity among Nigeria Christians is that the religion has become an object of mockery among unbelievers in Nigeria. When these cardinal assignments raised in this passage are addressed by Christians, the rule of the wicked and the corrupt holding the political progress of the nation held bound are expected to be dismantled.

Recommendations

Given the above-discussed challenges, Christianity as an agent of socialization is expected to embark on some reforms to be able to meet with the expectations of the populace on its roles towards political success. The following are some recommendations from this study:

- i. The Christians should be on the frontline in inculcating the moral virtues and values and making individuals imbibe these virtues of moral principles which include love, peace, forbearance, kindness, goodness, faithfulness and gentleness, self-control, obedience among others. This will go a long way to sanitize and help breed a better generation that would be capable of raising good leaders through viable electoral processes.
- ii. The Christians should encourage more Christians to go into politics. There is a need for good Christians to participate in politics: to vote and be voted for good governance. Christians must participate and non-participation is against God and humanity. The old missionary idea that Christians should have nothing to do with politics (come-ye-outism) should be discarded as it has deprived Nigerian Christians of their rights.
- iii. The researcher hereby recommends also, to all clergymen and Christian stakeholders in the Nigerian society, to help minimize the uncontrollable quest for material wealth by living an exemplary life worthy of emulation as Christians. This must begin with the leaders of the church. Collection of funds and other material favours from Christian politicians and non-Christian politicians should be discouraged by all, as this to some extent will minimize corruption within the church.

- iv. The ugly consequences of disunity among Christians in Nigeria should be a big challenge to all Christians. The research hereby calls for more unity among Christian brethren as this will be to the political interest of the nation Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study has examined Christianity in Nigeria and Political Challenges, 1960-2020. Christianity since its inception in Nigeria has indeed recorded massive, monumental and phenomenal achievements towards the development of the Nation. While it is very glaring that the faith is a blessing to Africa and Nigeria in particular, there is no denying the fact that the Christian religion has also come with some challenges to African societies. In recent times, Christianity has been accused of some social challenges it has brought on the Nigerian people.

One of the areas Christianity seems to have fallen short of its expectation is its contributions towards Nigerian politics in recent times. Christianity as a social agent of development in Africa and the world at large is expected to bring about more political development, especially in the areas of leadership and electoral processes for viable leaders into political offices in Nigeria. But for reasons like the early ignorance of the church on political issues in Nigeria, corruption, unhealthy quest for material wealth and disunity, Christianity in Nigeria has become encumbered with many distractions within its fold. Therefore, instead of standing tall to lead from every political front in this nation, the faith has been identified to have contributed to some of the political challenges that have impeded the growth and development of the nation. In order to achieve the aim of this study, efforts were made on the historical development of both Christianity as a religion and Nigeria as a state. Various contributions of Christianity towards the formation and integration of Nigeria have been well traced, not leaving behind some early roles of the Church in the early political process and leadership in Nigeria. The submission of this research is that Christianity will do better than what it did in the past for the nation, if the faith can sanitize itself in the areas accusing fingers have been pointed, as discussed above. Ways by which amendments can be made within the Church have been suggested in this study.

Endnotes

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